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Словосложение как способ образования неологизмов в английском языке

Аннотация. В статье исследуются новые лексические единицы, образованные в английском языке способом словосложения. Обсуждаются ключевые понятия, связанные с образованием сложных слов, такие как потенциальное слово, окказионализм, неологизм. Рассматриваются признаки сложных слов: порядок расположения компонентов и цельнооформленность. Определены особенности контаминации как вида словосложения. Выявлены основные группы новых лексических единиц, образованных способом словосложения: слова, состоящие из двух усеченных основ, из двух полных основ, из одной усеченной и одной полной. Подчеркивается значимость изучения и систематизации новой лексики, образованной способом словосложения.

Ключевые слова: новые слова, неологизмы, словообразование, словосложение, блендинг.

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Word composition as a way of forming neologisms in the English language

Abstract. In this article, new lexical units formed in the English language by word composition are examined. Key concepts related to the formation of compound words, such as a potential word, occasionalism, and neologism, are discussed. The features of compound words are considered: the order of the components and the unity of the word. The features of contamination as a type of compounding are determined. The main groups of new lexical units formed by word composition are revealed: words consisting of two shortened stems, two full stems, one shortened and one full. At the same time, the importance of studying and systematizing new vocabulary formed by compounding is emphasized.

Key words: new words, neologisms, word-building, composition, blending.

Словарный состав английского языка, как и многих других языков, постоянно изменяется и обновляется. Пополнение лексики происходит двумя способами: путем образования новых слов и путем заимствования слов из других языков. Основным источником пополнения словарного состава современного английского языка является словообразование.

Особый интерес лексикографов вызывает новая лексика. Следует отметить, что для обозначения новых лексических единиц лингвисты используют такие термины, как потенциальное слово, окказионализм, неологизм [1, с. 5]. Мы разделяем точку зрения тех, кто считает, что «неологизм – это заново созданное слово, которое является таковым, пока оно ощущается как новое носителями языка» [7, с. 5].

Среди лексикографических источников, фиксирующих новейшие лексические единицы, можно выделить электронные версии авторитетных англоязычных словарей, таких как Оксфордский и Кембриджский [9; 10]. Материалом для данной статьи послужили сложные слова-неологизмы, отобранные из этих словарей.

Один из продуктивных способов образования новой лексики – это словосложение. При словосложении соединяются две основы, которые по своей структуре могут быть корневыми, производными, сложными и даже сложнопроизводными.

Рассматривая особенности образования лексических единиц способом словосложения, многие лингвисты указывают на то, что порядок расположения компонентов в сложных словах строго фиксирован: первый компонент выступает как определяющее, а второй – как определяемое. При этом второй компонент, как правило, является структурным и семантическим центром сложного слова. Однако, не всегда различия между сложными словами и словосочетаниями столь очевидны [8, с. 3]. Следует также отметить, что важнейшим критерием слова является его цельнооформленность, следовательно, сложные слова, в отличие от словосочетаний, характеризуются слитным или дефисным написанием [2, с. 55].

Словосложение, как считают многие лингвисты, включает и контаминацию. Они по-разному трактуют это явление, используя такие термины, как «словослияние», «телескопия», «блендинг», «стяжение» и др. Количество контаминиро-

ванных слов, по данным исследований в области неологии, постоянно увеличивается. Слова, появляющиеся в результате словослияния, принято называть словами-слитками, или блендами (английский термин для данного способа *blending*) [6, с. 117]. Создание новой подобной единицы является результатом двустороннего деривационного процесса сложения и усечения любой из исходных единиц, каждая из которых представляет неотъемлемую часть слова-слитка [3, с. 6].

Самую значительную группу новой лексики составляют именно так называемые слова-слитки. Рассмотрим некоторые примеры.

Edimental *noun* a plant that is both *edible* and *ornamental*, and usually lives for several years.

e.g. *Harry Holding created an entire show garden at this year's Chelsea Flower Show based around the concept of edimentals. He explains the concept thus. "Edimentals are in the sweet spot of plants that both look nice, are edible, and generally live for three years or longer. Traditional food growing is more of a seasonal annual cycle, but with edimentals, once you've planted it or sown seeds, they are resilient and have longevity."* (*houseandgarden.co.uk*, 28 June 2023).

Proptech *noun* (*property+technology*) the business of using technology to buy and sell property in new ways.

e.g. *The real estate industry has undergone a significant technological transformation in recent years, and the word "proptech" has firmly come into common use. But this concept is so broad that you may even have no idea that the tool you're using actually refers to proptech. In fact, proptech real estate solutions apply to all processes throughout the lifecycle of a property* (*solve-it.dev*, 27 October 2023).

Приведенные примеры и подобные им слова-слитки позволяют согласиться с утверждением, что новые лексические единицы такого типа являются неотъемлемой частью рекламного дискурса, газетно-журнальной периодики, интерак-

тивной коммуникации и художественной литературы жанра фэнтези [4, с. 14].

Dexting *noun* exchanging many text messages with someone you have met on a dating app without ever meeting them in person.

e.g. *If you've ever found yourself in a back and forth texting marathon with a potential partner only to wind up with no actual in-person date to show for your time, you've probably been a victim of dexting. A combination of "dating" and "texting", dexting is when people form strong bonds over text after meeting on a dating app but never actually arrange a real date* (*glamourmagazine.co.uk*, 7 September 2023).

Ghostlighting *noun* the act of ending a relationship with someone by suddenly stopping all communication with them, then trying to make them believe that this did not actually happen and they must have imagined it.

e.g. *Ghostlighting mixes together ghosting – which is where a potential love interest disappears without an explanation – with the more sinister gaslighting, which is an emotional abuse or manipulation tool where a person purposefully tries to twist information to make their partner feel as though they are in the wrong* (*ww.mirror.co.uk*, 25 June 2023).

Traumedy *noun* a type of comedy that involves someone talking about past traumatic events in their life in a funny way.

e.g. *Standup has certainly taken a sharp turn towards inner trauma in recent years, giving rise to the dismissive portmanteau term "traumedy" to describe the comedic habit of processing disturbing experiences live on stage. And the 2023 Edinburgh fringe now looks like the peak of the trend* (*theguardian.com*, 20 August 2023).

Romantasy *noun* a type of fiction that combines elements of *romance* and *fantasy*.

e.g. *The American novelist is among a new generation of uber-bestselling authors writing "romantasy", a portmanteau of "romance" and "fantasy" applied to novels that blend elements of both genres ... Romantasy authors are selling well in part because of their huge popularity on social me-*

dia; Maas' publisher, Bloomsbury, says that videos with hashtags connected to her books have more than 14bn views on TikTok alone (theguardian.com, 2 February 2024).

Brotox *noun* a humorous word for Botox when the procedure is given to a man

e.g. *The rise of so-called Brotox is being reported in the UK, where the male grooming industry is worth an estimated £500 million a year. Celebrities aren't immune from this trend. Plastic surgeons say that more and more male stars appeared to be "jumping on the Brotox bandwagon" (theweek.com, 12 August 2023).*

Traptox *noun* a type of Botox injected into the trapezius muscle.

e.g. *The first time I saw a before and after pic of a traptox treatment, I immediately ran to the mirror to assess my shoulders. (For the uninitiated, traptox involves injecting a neurotoxin into your trapezius muscle to help relieve tension and possibly elongate your neck and slim your shoulders.) Over the next few weeks, I continued feeling hyper-aware and self-conscious about my shoulders as I saw an influx of traptox content on my Instagram feed (cosmopolitan.com, 1 January 2024).*

Рассмотрим примеры новых слов, где компоненты представлены полными основами, то есть они омонимичны словам, самостоятельно существующим в языке. Например:

Passphrase *noun* words that you must type into a computer or computer system in order to be able to use it.

e.g. *The longer your passphrase, the more secure it is.*

Healthspan *noun* the part of a person's life during which they are healthy (from health + span, apparently on the pattern of lifespan).

e.g. *The expert said that we need to extend our healthspan.*

Inchstone *noun* a small but important stage in the development of a baby or young child

e.g. *Pinterest predicts that in 2024, parents will focus on celebrating inchstones, which they describe as "tiny triumphs" ...*

Accomplishments like putting on shoes independently may not feel photo-worthy, but they still deserve to be celebrated. And parents who worked hard to help their children achieve those inchstones deserve to be celebrated, too (today.com, 12 January 2024).

Очевидно, что данная лексическая единица образовалась по аналогии со словом «milestone».

Runglasses *noun* a style of sunglasses that people sometimes wear when they are running.

e.g. *You were glued to the women's 100m final last night and are eagerly awaiting the heptathlon — is it time to hit the track yourself? Maybe not, but why not steal your favourite athlete's look instead? "Runglasses", those visor-style shades that the world's speediest can't get enough of, are turning out to be the summer accessory and are already a hit on the festival scene (thetimes.com, 4 August 2024).*

По аналогии с такими словами, как *greenwashing*, *sportswashing*, *whitewashing*, образованы следующие единицы:

Cloudwashing *noun* the act of marketing an old computer product or service as cloud-based when it is not, or mostly not, to take advantage of the popularity of cloud computing and make more money from the product or service.

e.g. *Cloud computing is low-maintenance, cost-effective and highly scalable — in fact, it's nothing short of game-changing. But if you're not vigilant, you could fall into the trap of procuring cloud software that's traditional software in disguise. It's called cloudwashing, and it's becoming more common (rae.co.za, 17 March 2024).*

Funwashing *noun* the practice of someone taking part in a popular event or show, appearing on television, etc. as a way to improve their reputation with the public.

e.g. *At the same time, former UK Independence Party leader Nigel Farage benefits from the same "funwashing" on "I'm a Celebrity Get me out of Here!" as Pauline Hanson, leader of the most successful ex-*

treme right party in Australia in recent years, did when she was invited on “Dancing with the Stars” just a moment after her political career plummeted (thewire.in, 27 November 2023).

Screenwashing *noun* the practice of someone appearing on a popular television programme as a way to improve their reputation with the general public.

e.g. *We need a word for the way political figures who have done terrible things are rehabilitated by television. So here’s a candidate: Screenwashing... Screenwashing induces us to forget or trivialise what these people did when they were in politics. It wipes the public memory clean. If you seek to remind people what these figures did when they were in politics, you are considered a spoilsport, a killjoy. This is the way the world ends: not with a bang but a bant (twitter.com/GeorgeMonbiot, 29 November 2022).*

Wokewashing *noun* behaviour or activities to make people believe that a company cares more about social problems such as racism and inequality than it really does.

e.g. *Enter wokewashing. In this phase, brands are co-opting social justice issues like anti-racism, feminism, inequality and mental health awareness. They align themselves with trending socially conscious and cultural issues. Meanwhile, some of the same (or similar) issues they speak up against are being perpetrated within their own company and their supply chains. Such is the dubious art of wokewashing (ecostyles.com.au, 23 February 2022).*

Friendlord *noun* someone who rents out a room in their house to a friend.

e.g. *There’s limited data on friendlords, but we know the number of homeowners taking in lodgers has tripled in the last ten years. Housing expert Vicky Spratt notes: “Troublingly, such agreements are as commonplace as they are flimsy, with homeowners from younger generations renting out rooms to lodgers and friends to cover their mortgages” (thelead.uk, 26 January 2023).*

Trendbait *noun* a new term or concept created to attract attention on social media platforms and start a trend.

e.g. *Trendbait describes the influx of slang for slang’s sake, where people create slang terms or new phrases in the hopes of going viral ... Trendbait leans into internet FOMO – the fear of missing out. It helps generate language which bonds niche communities on the internet. And, where relevant, brands can lean into this language to connect with their target audience (brand-watch.com, 6 June 2023).*

Grand-mate *noun* a grandparent who shares a home with a grandchild, or a grandchild who shares a home with a grandparent.

e.g. *This new “grand-mates” trend is bringing about some truly heartwarming intergenerational bonding. The New York Times profiled a number of families who are “grand-mates,” and not one of them had complaints about it. The worst thing they could say was that sometimes the grandchildren weren’t as tidy as their grandparents would like. But there’s an easy solution: One grandma said, “I just keep the door to [my granddaughter’s] room closed.” (al-eteia.org, 10 November 2022).*

Zero-dose a zero-dose child is one who has never received any of the routine vaccinations that most children are given.

e.g. *Since 2019, there has been a dramatic increase in the number of zero-dose children globally due to COVID-19 disruptions, increased economic crises and conflict, and declines in vaccine confidence ... To turn the tide on this unprecedented increase in zero-dose children, it is essential to know who and where these children are so we can reach every child with life-saving vaccinations (data.unicef.org, April 2023).*

Среди выявленных неологизмов встречаются также образованные от сложения двух основ, одна из которых усеченная, а другая полная. Например, первая основа полная, а вторая усеченная:

Coolcation *noun* a holiday in a place where the weather is not very warm, usually because you do not want to go somewhere that has become too hot because of climate change.

e.g. *For the vast majority of folk, summer holidays used to be about following the sun, seeking the heat. With the intense, rec-*

ord-breaking temperatures of recent years, however, many are considering travelling in the opposite direction: booking “coolcations” in temperate destinations, which also benefit from being less crowded (cntraveler.com, 18 December 2023).

Slowcation *noun* a type of holiday where the aim is to get to know the people and culture of a place slowly, rather than simply visiting the most popular tourist attractions.

e.g. Embarking on a slowcation is like savoring a fine wine; it’s about indulging in the depth, complexity, and subtlety of a place, rather than merely skimming its surface. Instead of racing through a checklist of attractions, a slowcation invites you to linger, to delve into the heart of a destination. It’s about finding the soul of a place, living like a local, and allowing the rhythm of everyday life to dictate your days (driftravel.com, 13 December 2023).

Haycation *noun* a holiday spent on a farm, during which the guests sometimes help out with the farm work.

e.g. Check out of the city life for a few days and check into a stay that’s raw, real, and rural. A haycation on a family-owned farm is good for the soul and a fast track to connecting with a more grounded way of life. Pack the car, pop on some hard-wearing denim, and spend a few nights at any one of these regional stays (www.australiasgoldenoutback.com, 15 February 2023).

Warmdrobe *noun* a collection of warm clothes to wear in cold weather.

e.g. Finessing the art of cold weather dressing in winter is hard work, but a warmdrobe will make it decidedly easier. The key to a warmdrobe – a wardrobe curated specifically for bitterly cold times such as these – lies in tri- and quad-layering. This is the practice of acquiring pieces that need as little thought as possible because you know you can rely on them to do all of the heavy lifting for you (stylist.co.uk, January 2024).

Tipflation *noun* the increase in the amount of money that people are expected

to give as a tip.

e.g. An increase in tipping has come as part of a post covid world, and gratitude is not the only reason for the rise. A change in the way we live (and hygiene concerns) has played its part in forming tipflation. Human interaction in the hospitality sector reduced massively and now we have mostly moved to ordering, paying and tipping for food digitally (kiplinger.com, 11 May 2023).

Cheapflation *noun* the situation when the price of a product stays the same or increases but its main ingredient is present in a smaller amount or lower quality.

e.g. A number of major brands stocking chocolate, sauces, fish, meat, and other products in France have been accused of “cheapflation” by a leading consumer watchdog. Under “cheapflation” the amount of a product’s ingredient (sometimes the main part) decreases significantly, or is replaced with a lower quality, cheaper and often healthier alternative. At the same time, however, the price of the product increases (connexionfrance.com, 7 February 2024).

Среди новейшей лексики выделяются и другие слова со вторым компонентом - *flation*: *greedflation*, *ripflation*, *skimpflation* [5, с. 151].

Boomerocracy *noun* the idea that society is structured in a way that means people born between approximately 1945 and 1965 have the most influence and power.

e.g. One idea you touch on is the “boomerocracy” – a notion that society is organised for boomers. Is that how you see things? I went to the Metropolitan Opera recently to see La bohème. It’s about poor people, but the only people who could afford to go to see it were those with lots of money. These sorts of things are organised by this “boomerocracy” (BBC History Magazine, 8 June 2023).

Flextirement *noun* an arrangement where an employee gradually reduces their working hours until they completely retire.

e.g. Instead of a full-blown retirement when you reach 62 years old and can collect social security benefits, flextirement allows

an employee to move to a more part-time role and eventually shorten the number of hours worked over a certain time period until they officially retire. Instead of working a full 40-hour week, that person might switch to only half that, leaving them time to begin to enjoy retirement (worklife. news, 30 October 2023).

Spathroom *noun* a bathroom that has been designed to be very clean, comfortable and relaxing, like a spa.

e.g. More people are looking to incorporate wellness into their home, particularly in the bathroom. The focus is on creating a “spathroom”, a bathroom/spa hybrid that promotes serenity and calm. Good lighting is a spathroom essential, as light has a huge effect on our wellbeing (county.wedding, 24 February 2023).

Wanderpreneur *noun* someone who does not have a permanent office or home and spends time living with their family and working in different towns or countries.

e.g. I'm here with three kids in tow, making me part of a growing trend for “wanderpreneurs”: digital nomads but all grown-up. Have kids, will travel. For wanderpreneurs, this is a nomadic life but with structure: children are occupied during the day so adults can earn money (Sunday Times, 24 March 2024).

Robotherapist *noun* a robot that can massage someone to treat pain and injury, in a similar way to a physiotherapist.

e.g. Enter the Backhug: a robotic therapist equipped with 26 mechanical fingers to scan the unique curvature of your spine and press away stiffness in the joints of your back, neck and shoulders. When I was invited to try one of these “robotherapists”, I jumped at the chance. Despite taking regular exercise, I suffer from many complaints, and was intrigued to see what difference six weeks of daily massage could make (theguardian.com, 7 July 2023).

Как видно из вышеприведенных примеров, преобладают единицы, где первый компонент представлен полной основой, а второй – усеченной. Но есть немногочисленные слова, где усекается первый компонент. Например:

Lisness *noun* a type of travel where a longer holiday will include some time spent working, attending a business conference etc.

e.g. Between business and pleasure, we've identified a paradigm shift that we call “lisness”. The reverse of the old way – of tacking a day or two of relaxation onto a business trip – this is about planning a leisure trip and creating time in which to work. We're seeing client travels extending into month-long ventures, with a 75/25 leisure/business split. With time to labour and time to lounge (or explore). (blacktomato.com, 30 May 2023).

В словарях можно увидеть сложные слова, с компонентом e-, помимо привычного e-mail: *e-bike, e-book, e-business, e-card*. В качестве новых единиц словари дают, например:

E-banking *noun (also internet banking)* [uncountable] activities relating to your bank account that you do using the internet.

e.g. The e-banking system connects banks to digital wallets and electronic payment platforms.

E-gate *noun* a machine at an airport for checking passports.

e.g. Make sure you take off your hat when using an e-gate.

Оригинальными представляются лексические единицы, образованные путем сложения двух основ, одна из которых представлена именем собственным. Например:

Quit-Tok *noun* a trend on TikTok where people post videos about quitting their job, often commenting on the lack of job satisfaction or work–life balance that was the reason for their resignation.

e.g. Quit-Tok refers to the trend of employees, primarily Generation Z, sharing videos of their resignation or layoff stories publicly ... on TikTok. These videos often capture the raw emotion of the moment, from the tense build-up to the liberating feeling of finally quitting a job. Quit-Tok videos vary in format, from filming live Zoom resignations to documenting the moment a resignation letter is handed in (peoplemattersglobal.com, 10 August 2024).

WaterTok *noun* a community on the social media service TikTok where people post videos of recipes for water mixed with different flavoured ingredients.

e.g. *Welcome to “WaterTok,” one of the latest trends taking over timelines. People are creating cocktails of flavored syrups, powder packets, ice, and, obviously, water (traditionally in their large Stanley cups) in an effort to boost their daily water intake (fastcompany.com, 11 April 2024).*

Swiftonomics *noun* the impact on the economy of a city or country caused by the singer Taylor Swift and her popularity.

e.g. *Swiftonomics refers to the economic influence of musician Taylor Swift. In 2023, Swift embarked on her Eras Tour, a global series of shows that has become the highest-grossing tour on record, with a gross of more than \$1 billion so far. The Eras Tour has been credited with boosting local economies across the U.S. ... The pop*

superstar and her international tour also affected the global economy (investopedia.com, 8 March 2024).

Очевидно, такие примеры единичны, однако они отражают современные тенденции.

Таким образом, словосложение остается одним из наиболее продуктивных способов образования новой лексики в английском языке. Основные группы новых лексических единиц, образованных способом словосложения, составляют слова, состоящие из двух усеченных основ, двух полных основ, одной усеченной и одной полной. Представленный материал демонстрирует лишь отдельный пласт словарного состава современного английского языка, который постоянно видоизменяется и пополняется. Новая лексика, очевидно, требует изучения и систематизации.

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